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**ROLE OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION – A REVIEW
STUDY**

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Abstract

Pregnancy is a life-changing event in every woman's life with regard to physical as well as psychological aspects. Postpartum period has lots of challenges as dealing with traumatic childbirth, developing bond with their child at the same time coping with new routine. Due to these challenges postpartum period is highly prone to psychological depression. Postpartum depression (PPD) affects around 10% of women, or 1 in 7 women, after giving birth. *Yoga* is a practise of set of postures and mindful therapies, which relieves mind-body stress that maintains mental and physical health. *Yoga* therapy incorporates practices like *Pranadharna*, subtle exercises, *Asana*, *Pranayama* and *Dhyana*. The science of *Yoga* also focuses on unity of mind and body.

Key Words:

Postpartum depression, Yogic postures, and mindful practices

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INTRODUCTION:

Women are more prone to develop psychological disorders due to change in hormonal level starting from puberty to menopause, many physical as well as psychological changes fall out. Pregnancy is one of the milestones in every woman's life. Childbirth provokes a variety of psychiatric illnesses including mood disorders. "Postpartum mood disorders" range of emotional and psychological changes that women experience after childbirth including baby blues, postpartum depression, and puerperal psychosis.ⁱ Postpartum disorder is a significant social issue which affects mothers and their families.ⁱⁱ

According to WHO, worldwide about 10% of pregnant women and 13% of women who have just given birth experience a mental disorder, primarily depression. In developing countries this is even higher, i.e. 15.6% during pregnancy and 19.8% after child birth. In severe cases mother's suffering might be so severe that they may even commit suicide.ⁱⁱⁱ In India, about 22% of mothers suffer from postpartum depression.

At present, Postpartum depression is not classified as a separate disease in its own right: it is diagnosed as part of effective or mood disorders in both DSM-V (American Psychiatric Association) and ICD-10.^{iv} The exact cause of PPD is unspecified, however, combination of physical, emotional, genetic, and social factors such as hormone imbalances and sleep deprivation may all play a role. Changes in the hypo thalmo-pituitary-adrenal axis may be a cause manifested by loss of energy and appetite, insomnia, social withdrawal, irritability, and even suicidal attitude.^v High risk factors for postpartum illness are past as well as of family history of psychiatric illness, young age pregnancy, traumatic childbirth.

Bipolar disorder along with depressive disorder after first childbirth, provides shelter for recurrence of postpartum depression. One study reported the recurrence rate at 100% following delivery among women who had a bipolar depressive episode after their first delivery. Undiagnosed PPD was observed among 50% of mothers, which may due to stigma of mental illness in society which arises poor infant attachment; cognitive, emotional and behavioural problems in children that may last through adulthood, poor performance of infant safety measures, poor infant growth and decreased breastfeeding.^{vi}

If there is no adjustment in the stressful situation, the reactions will be inappropriate and will cause negative consequences such as anger, misconduct, disturbed sleep patterns, malfunction, and isolation. *Yoga* a holistic science which incorporates practices like *Pranadharna*, subtle exercises, *Asana*, *Pranayama* and *Dhyana*. *Yoga* focuses on physical as well as psychological wellbeing of the individuals.

Aim:

To explore the efficacy of *Yoga* in Postpartum depression (PPD).

Objectives:

To evaluate the action of *Yogic* postures and mindful practices on Postpartum depression (PPD).

Materials and Methods:

In order to carry out this review study, different Classical Ayurvedic literatures and Modern textbooks

having references related to Postpartum depression were searched. Different electronic databases including Google Scholar, PubMed, the Ayush research portal, and DHARA were searched using keywords like Postpartum depression (PPD).

Name of database	Search terms	Number of articles
Pub med central	Postpartum depression and Yoga	32
	postpartum depression and mindfulness	22
Science direct	Postpartum depression	12
Google Scholar	Postpartum depression and Yoga	335
Ayush research portal	Postpartum depression	01

Review of literature:

PPD is a psychological mood disorder, the cause of PPD is unknown but there are some trigger factors which likely prone to develop PPD. If the PPD is left untreated, it further leads to poor mother and infant bonding which may last through adulthood also, long term effect on child development.

Lack of family support, financial difficulties, poor marital relationship, are the main risk factors for developing postpartum stress which give rise to depression. Recognizing the risk factors at initial stages helps to lower down the long-term harmful effect. Many *Ayurveda* regimens like *Sootika-Paricharya*, Lifestyle modification, *Satwavajaya chikitsa*, *Shamana chikitsa*, *Yoga* and *Pranayama* has been intervened. The most common aspects of *Yoga* today are different techniques of bodily postures (*Asanas*) and breathing exercises (*Pranayama*), concentration (Meditation). Being holistic, it is the best means for achieving physical, mental, social and spiritual wellbeing.

Articles critically reviewed:

1. A Review on Therapeutic Intervention of Yoga and Ayurveda in Post-Partum Depression. (<https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=116066>)
2. Postpartum Depression: The Role of Ayurveda in Prevention and Intervention (https://ijbpas.com/pdf/2022/March/MS_IJBPAS_2022_MARCH_SPCL_1030.pdf)
3. Concept of Maternal Mental Health in Ayurveda: A Review (https://ijrap.net/admin/php/uploads/2355_pdf.pdf)
4. Perceived Postpartum Stress and Coping Strategies Among Postnatal Mothers at Aims, Kochi (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321493793_Perceived_postpartum_stress_and_coping_strategies_among_postnatal_mothers_at_aims_Kochi)
5. Integrated Yoga as a first line treatment for Antenatal and Postnatal Mental Health (<https://jaims.in/jaims/article/view/2280/2953>)

Result and Discussion:

Yoga as alternative medicine, incorporates mind-body practices. *Yoga* not only focus on spiritual aspect but also physio – psychological aspect of well -being of individual. *Hath yoga* practices i.e. eight limbs of *Yoga Yama* (Ethical guidance), *Niyama* (Spiritual observances), *Asana* (Physical poses), *Pranayama* (Breathing exercise), *Pratyahara* (Control of the senses), *Dharana* (Concentration), *Dhyana* (Meditation), *Samadhi* (State of bliss)^{vii} are beneficial.

Due to exposure to stressful condition, psychological tension arises which also leads to physical tension. Stress gets reflected on muscles, results in contraction, fails to co-ordinate properly, disturb the harmony of mind and body. The main objective of *Asana* is to maintain harmony of mind and body by reducing stress, strain and tension. Some *Asana* practices like *Shavasana* (corpse pose), *Balasana* (child pose), both the relaxative pose aims at release the tension at the level of subconsciousness. Relaxative asanas when performed for 10-15 minutes, all the tensed muscles, joints are relaxed, improves venous circulation, tones the whole nervous system relieves fatigue. *Uttanpadasana* (Raised leg pose) helps to strengthen the spine, improve spinal flexibility, tone the abdominal muscles which is over all helps to tone the muscles which are strained during the pregnancy.

Breathing practice like *Nadi shodhana pranayama* (alternate nostril breathing), right nostril breathing i.e. *Pingala nadi* activates the sympathetic nervous system and left nostril i.e. *Ida nadi* activates the parasympathetic nervous system, which brings the balance in autonomic nervous system.^{viii} By practicing the concentration of breathing through *Pranayama*, one can de-stress the mind and evoke the relax state of mind. Also, purify the *Nadi*, excellent for detoxification.

Mindfulness practice like *Dharana*, *Dhyana* is a valuable tool helps to regulate their emotions, reduces the feeling of overwhelm and increases emotional resilience. Also, promotes a sense of calm and relaxation. Variation in HPA axis is one of the causes of PPD. HPA axis plays a crucial role in body's response to stress. Mindful practices appear to be associated with improved regulation of the sympathetic nervous system and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system.^{ix}

Conclusion:

Period following the birth of a child and lasting approximately six weeks refers to postnatal period, its most crucial period but gets neglected. PPD affects maternal morbidity and mortality and also, child development. Postnatal women suffer from mood disorders as depression in attaining mother role, dealing with household chores, lack of support, physical body changes etc. Postpartum screening with addressing the risk factors at initial stage helps to combat the depression.

Several aspects of *Yoga* (such as *Asana*, and *Pranayama*, *Dhyana*, etc.) imparts physical as well as psychological effect helps to overcome depression, restores the strength, and relieves the mental stress. *Shavasana* (corpse pose) and *Balsana* (child pose) relaxative postures, relaxes the mind-body at subconscious level, breathing practice like *Nadi shodhana pranayama* (alternate nostril breathing), purify the *Nadi* and evoke relax state of mind. Mindfulness practice like *Dharana*, *Dhyana* promotes a sense of calm and relaxation. *Yoga* being non pharmacological and cost- effective intervention, it helps to combat the depression. Also, it is safe in antenatal and postnatal period.

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